

CERAMIC-METAL HYBRID PARTICLES AS FILLERS LEADING TO ENHANCED DIELECTRIC PERFORMANCE OF THE POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Polymeric composites with high dielectric constant (high-k) have found their applications in energy storage devices, actuators, organic field transistors, and embedded capacitors etc. The ceramic/polymer composites are most widely used, which however, suffer a low dielectric constant (<100) even with a high filler loading (>50vol%). In contrast, the composites containing conductors as fillers could exhibit a colossal dielectric constant but accompanied with a high dielectric loss. Using ceramic-metal hybrids as fillers, of which the nano metal particles are discretely grown on the ceramic grain surface, is a new strategy leading to enhanced dielectric constant and low dielectric loss.

In this research, composites consisted of heterogeneous BaTiO₃-supporting Ag (BT-Ag) hybrid fillers and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) polymer matrix were prepared. BT-Ag hybrid particles were synthesized via a seed-mediated growing process by a redox reaction between silver nitrate and ethylene glycol. Investigations were carried out on how to achieve desirable dielectric properties by controlling the size and amount of the silver nanoparticles on BT surface, based on different size of BT. The results showed that the size of the deposited nano Ag increased with the size of BT particle. The sizes of the discretely deposited Ag nanoparticles were 20~30 nm, 50~70 nm and 70~90 nm on the 100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm BT, respectively, which in consequence, affected the dielectric properties of the composites. The BT-Ag/PVDF with 300 nm BT show better dielectric behavior than the composites with 100 nm and 500 nm BT. A dielectric constant of 235 was obtained with (300nm) BT-(50~70nm)Ag and the dielectric loss was 0.11 at 1 kHz, demonstrating promising applications in the electronic devices.

1 INTRODUCTION

Flexible polymeric composites with high performance of dielectric properties are desired in high-density electronic packaging technology^[1], to be incorporated in the organic substrates for applications of energy storage^[2], noise suppression, filtering, decoupling, and bypassing etc^[3]. The composites can maintain excellent mechanical property, high electrical breakdown strength, and chemical stability of polymer matrix, while desired dielectric properties can be tailored by choosing and adjusting the filler particles. In order to follow the miniaturization requirement and ensure good performance of the electronic devices, dielectric polymeric materials with high dielectric constant and relatively low dielectric loss are highly desired.^[4] The dielectric constant of polymer usually has a low value of less than 10. Ferroelectric ceramics and conductive particles are the two kinds to be used as filler in the polymeric composites^[5-8]. While the ceramic/polymer composite has relatively low dielectric constant and dielectric loss, the conductor/polymer is vice versa, and as a result neither is promising for the future applications.^[9] For the composites containing conductor as fillers, both dielectric constant and

loss show abrupt increase at the percolation threshold. Therefore, strategies are needed to maintain high dielectric constant and meanwhile suppress the dielectric loss.

Recently, we have demonstrated that the dielectric performance can be well enhanced by using the hybrid structure of Ag-deposited BT hybrid particles (BT-Ag).^[10] The Ag nanoparticles were discretely distributed on the surface of BT, which prevented formation of conductive path and suppressed the increase of dielectric loss. In order to further understand the dielectric mechanism and explore higher performance of this type of composites, in this study, the BT size (100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm) effect on the deposition of nano Ag and the dielectric properties of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) and ethylene glycol purchased from Shanghai Lingfeng Chemical Co. Ltd. were used as the precursor of Ag and reducing agent, respectively. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPK30, Mw=10,000 g/mol, Urchem Chemical Co. China) was used as the capping agent. BaTiO_3 nanoparticles with the sizes of 100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm (Shandong Guoci Functional Materials Co. China.) were used as the supporting particles for Ag deposition. Poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF, Shanghai 3F Co. China) was chosen as the polymer matrix due to its high dielectric constant and easy processing.

2.2. Fabrication of samples

Firstly, Ag-deposited BT hybrid particles were prepared by the reduction of silver nitrate with glycol solution in BaTiO_3 (BT) suspension.^[11] An appropriate amount of PVP (0.5g) and AgNO_3 (5g) were dissolved in 300ml ethylene glycol. Then it was heated up in an oil bath from room temperature to 180°C and kept for 1h. The obtained BT-Ag suspension was cooled down to room temperature and washed by absolute ethanol for three times. The precipitate of BT-Ag particles was dried at room temperature for 24h.

Secondly, the BT-Ag hybrid particles were employed to PVDF powders and mixed with a certain amount of ethanol solution. After ultrasonic treatment for 1h, the dispersion was stirred for 1h, and then dried at 70°C for 12 h in an oven. The mixture powder was milled and then moulded by hot pressing to prepare the BT-Ag/PVDF composites. At about 180°C under a pressure of 10MPa, a tablet sample with 11mm in diameter and about 1mm in thickness was obtained. Conductive silver paste was painted on both sides as electrodes.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology of BT-Ag particles was examined by scanning electron microscope (Nova Nano SEM450). Dielectric property evaluation was carried out using an impedance analyzer (Agilent, 4294A) in the frequency range of 100 Hz–10 MHz at room temperature. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD, D/max-2500/PC, Rigaku Co.) with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=0.154$ nm) and 40 kV of acceleration voltage applied in the 2θ range of 10° ~80° .

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of BT-Ag hybrids

Figure 1 (a~c) SEM images of BT-Ag hybrids with the BT size of 100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm, respectively. (d) HRTEM pattern of the 100nm BT-Ag particle.

SEM images of BT-Ag hybrids with different BT size were shown in Figure 1(a~c). For the three types of BT-Ag hybrids, nano Ag particles are randomly grown on the surface of BT particles. With the increase of BT size, the quantity of Ag nanoparticles deposited on the surface of BT decreases, while the size of Ag increases. The sizes of Ag nanoparticles deposited on BT (100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm) are 20~30 nm, 50~70 nm and 70~90 nm, respectively. The HRTEM image of an individual BT-Ag hybrid (Figure 1d) shows that the silver particle has a lattice spacing of 2.40 Å, characteristic of the (1 1 1) planes. The BT grain shows a lattice spacing of 2.33 Å, characteristic of the (1 1 1) planes. The BT and Ag particles are well intercrossed at the interface.

The crystal phase of BT particles is related with their particle size. The crystal phase is cubic when the size is 100 nm or below and it is tetragonal for the 300 nm and 500 nm ones.^[12] We have demonstrated that the similar lattice spacing of (1 1 1) planes of BT and Ag is key for the heteroepitaxial growth.^[10] So, it means that the effective site for Ag nanoparticle deposition on BT surface is dependent on the quantity of (1 1 1) planes of BT particles. The shape of BT particles is nearly sphere for 100 nm, and turns to square for 300 nm and 500 nm, meaning that the amount of active sites for Ag deposition is decreased with BT size. As a result, the content of Ag deposited on big size of BT is reduced.

Besides, the initial concentration of Ag ions during preparation for the three sizes BT was same, and reacted at the same temperature. The Ag nanoparticles were firstly hetero-epitaxially grown on BT surface. Then, with the concentration of Ag crystal nuclei increased, the Ag nanoparticles would grow through homogeneous nucleation. The less of active sites for Ag deposition, the less of crystal nucleus consumed in the hetero-epitaxial growth process. The excess silver crystal nuclei were then consumed in the homogeneous nucleation process. Therefore, the Ag particle size became larger on big size BT due to less active sites of exposed (111) planes.

3.2 Effects of BT size and BT-Ag filler loading amount on the electrical properties

Figure 2 Variation of (a) dielectric constant and (b) loss of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites as a function of filler loading at 1 kHz; Dependence of conductivity of 300nm BT-Ag/PVDF on (c) filler loading amount and (d) frequency.

High dielectric constant and low loss of BT-Ag filled PVDF composites are expected based on the point that Ag particles can enhance the polarization of BT and localized Ag particles prevent the formation of conductive paths in the composites. The variation of dielectric properties of BT-Ag/PVDF composites as a function of filler loading is shown in Figure 2. The dielectric constant (Figure 2a) is enhanced with the increase of filler loading. The tendency is much like that of the ceramic filled polymer composites,^[13] and no percolation is observed although the Ag nanoparticles were contained in the composites. It suggests that there is no conductive path forming in the composites. The dielectric constants of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites show almost same values when the filler loading is lower than 60 wt%. The difference of dielectric constants between the three composites becomes obvious as the filler loading is further increased. The composites filled with 300 nm BT-Ag hybrids achieve highest dielectric constant of about 235 at 1 kHz with the filler loading of 80 wt%. With the same content of BT-Ag, the dielectric constants of 100 nm BT-Ag and 500 nm BT-Ag were 98 and 133, respectively. The enhanced dielectric constants for all the three types of composites should be mainly caused by the intrinsic polarization, as well as the induced polarization of BT. The intrinsic polarization of BT is increased with the increasing size of BT due to the transformation of the crystal phase from cubic to tetragonal. The induced polarization is proportional to the amount of Ag particles attached to the BT surface. Thus, the 500 nm BT has the highest intrinsic polarization and 100 nm BT the highest induced polarization. However, the 300 nm BT-Ag hybrids show the highest polarization due to the combination of intrinsic and induced polarization.

The variation tendency of dielectric loss as a function of filler loading is similar to the dielectric constant as shown in Figure 2b. With the increase of filler loading, the dielectric loss increases with the filler loading. The highest dielectric loss is 0.11 for 300 nm BT-Ag filled PVDF composite with the filler content of 80 wt%. With the same filler loading, the dielectric losses for the 100 nm BT-Ag and 500 nm BT-Ag hybrids filled composites are 0.061 and 0.057, respectively. All of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites show low dielectric losses. The dielectric loss below or at 1 kHz is mainly caused by the relaxation of interfacial polarization.^[14] The conductive loss can be neglected in the composites because no conductive path has formed, which is supported by the variation tendency of conductivity as a function of filler loading as shown in Figure 2c. Figure 2d confirms that the 300nm BT-Ag/PVDF composites with varied filler loading show low conductivity and maintain the insulating properties over the frequency range of 100Hz~1MHz. The above results indicate that hybrid structure of Ag deposited on the surface of BT effectively prevented the formation of conductive paths, leading to enhanced dielectric constant and suppressed loss.

3.2 Frequency dependence of BT-Ag/PVDF composites

Figure 3 Frequency dependence of the dielectric properties of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites measured at room temperature.

The frequency dependence of the dielectric properties of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites at room temperature is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3(a~c) present the variation of dielectric constant with frequency from 100 Hz to 10 MHz. When the filler content is lower than 70 wt%, the dielectric constants of all the three BT-Ag/PVDF composites are relatively stable with the increase of frequency. When the filler content is increased to 80 wt%, the dielectric constant decreases remarkably with frequency. The high dielectric constant at low frequency is mainly attributed to the interfacial polarization.^[14,15] The interfacial polarization originates from the interface between the filler and PVDF polymer matrix. High filler loading produces more interfaces that enhance the contribution of interfacial polarization to the dielectric constant. Significantly, among the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites, 300 nm BT-Ag/PVDF shows the most apparent decrease with frequency. However, the interfacial area is reduced with the BT size because the specific surface area is inversely proportional to the particle size. It indicates that the induced polarization makes contribution to the dielectric constant in addition to the interfacial polarization. The Ag nanoparticles on BT surface could enhance the induced polarization of BT as the electric field is applied. The dielectric constants of the composites with 100 nm, 300 nm and 500 nm BT-Ag hybrids are 66, 149.6 and 86, respectively, with the filler loading of 80 wt% at 10 MHz. The results indicate that the BT-Ag hybrids filled composites can maintain high dielectric constant at high frequency which is especially desired in real application.

Figure 3 (d~f) show the variation of dielectric loss as a function of frequency. At low frequency (<100 kHz), the dielectric loss decreases with the increase of frequency and increases with the filler content. However, at higher frequency (> 100 kHz), the dielectric loss increases with frequency and decreases with the filler content. The dielectric loss is originated from two different polarization mechanisms in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 10 MHz. One is the interfacial polarization between different phases. The other is the dipole polarization of the PVDF matrix. At low frequencies, the dielectric loss is mainly caused by the relaxation of interfacial polarization, and the dielectric loss decreases with frequency. At the same time, with the increase of filler content, the interfacial

polarization is enhanced which results in higher dielectric loss. On the contrary, the dielectric loss is controlled by the dipole polarization of the PVDF matrix at higher frequencies. Besides, the dipole polarization of PVDF is proportional to the content of PVDF in the composites. The content of PVDF is reduced with increasing the filler content. As a result, the dielectric loss is reduced with filler loading in the high frequency range. The maximum value of dielectric loss of the three types of BT-Ag/PVDF composites in the full frequency range is lower than 0.252, which is comparable with the BT filled PVDF composites.^[16]

4 CONCLUSIONS

Three types of BT-Ag hybrids were synthesized and the dielectric properties of the PVDF composites were investigated. Ag-deposited BT hybrid structure restricted the formation of conductive path and enhanced the induced polarization of BT, which resulted in high dielectric constant and low dielectric loss of the BT-Ag/PVDF composites. By tailoring the microstructure and size of BT-Ag hybrids, high performance of dielectric properties was obtained in the 300 nm BT-Ag/PVDF. The dielectric constant and loss of the composite at 1 kHz and room temperature were 235 and 0.11, respectively.

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